

Deliverable 6.3

Visual identity and project website

FEDORA - Future-oriented Science EDucation
to enhance Responsibility and engagement
in the society of Acceleration and uncertainty

Visual identity and project website

Due date: 28 February 2021

Actual submission date: 30/03/2021

Project start date: 01/09/2020 - Duration: 36

months Work Package concerned: WP6

Concerned work package leader: Francesca Conti

Task leader: Formicablu

Authors: Andrea Troncoso, Elisabetta Tola, Francesca Conti

Dissemination level:

- **PU: X**
- CO:
- CI:

Quality assurance

To ensure the quality and correctness of this deliverable, we implied an internal review and validation process. The deliverable was drafted by the work package leader (formicablu). All partners contributed to and reviewed the overall draft. Finally, the semi-final version was submitted to the project coordinator for a final review and validation.

Version	Date	Status	Author	
V0	03/02/2021	Draft	Formicablu A. Troncoso	Creation of the document
V1	08/02/2021	First internal revision	Formicablu E. Tola, F. Conti	Integration of the document
V2	11/02/2021	Sharing with the consortium	All partners commented	Corrections suggestions and edits
V3	18/02/2021	Sharing with Coordinator	UNIBO O. Levrini, I. Carbone	First round of comments and corrections
V4 uploaded	30/03/2021	Final version	Formicablu A. Troncoso, F. Conti, E. Tola UNIBO O.Levrini, I.Carbone	Final edits, transfer to graphic layout – upload.pdf

2. ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
EC	European Commission
H2020	Horizon 2020 framework and funding programme
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna, Coordinator
FB	formicablu, WP6 leader
KTU	Kauno Technology University
UH	University of Helsinki
UOXF	University of Oxford
TTF	Teach the Future Foundation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
R&I	Research and Innovation

3. PROJECT OVERVIEW

FEDORA will develop a future-oriented model to enable formal and informal science education to equip the young with thinking, foresight and action competence skills needed to grapple with the societal challenges.

In particular, the project aims to address three forms of misalignment that emerge from the difficulties of the educational systems to keep the pace of societal changes: a) the clash between, on the one hand, the vertical and hyper-specialised organisation of teaching in disciplines and, on the other, the inter-multi-transdisciplinary, multi-actor and open character of the new modus operandi of R&I; b) the mismatch between the formalised and exclusive languages used in schools and the needs for new languages to enhance imagination and the capacity to talk about the contemporary challenges; c) the clash between the a-temporal or historically oriented teaching approaches and the need to support the young to construct visions of the future that empower actions in the present. These forms of misalignment represent blind spots for science education that FEDORA will explore through a multi-layer (institutional, conceptual, cultural) research approach, articulated structures of actions and a multiform set of research methodologies. The actions and results will feed into recommendations for anticipatory policies aimed to mobilise visionary attitudes on open-schooling and orient concrete institutional transformations to nurture, in secondary school students, a new sense of trust and desire needed to support an aware, responsible and sustainable participation in science-related societal issues. FEDORA's main objective is to align science education with the fast-changing society and with R&I. This overarching goal is articulated into four general objectives, summarised here:

1. Contribute to aligning the traditional educational institutions with the ways R&I is produced;
2. Contribute to aligning (informal, non-formal and formal) science education with the society of acceleration;
3. Contribute to "futurising" science education;
4. Support the young generation to increase their personal and public engagement in science, their employability and hope, trust, desire, visionary and proactive moods in this accelerated, multi-velocity, complex and uncertain society.

Deliverable D6.3, as defined in Task 6.3: “**Visual identity and project website**” of Work Package 6 “Behind the scenes: communicating and disseminating FEDORA in its making” is closely connected to Deliverable 6.1 “**Communication and Dissemination Plan**” and serves its objectives, which comprise the following:

1. Ensure effective communication and dissemination of the project: internal communication and outreach;
2. Provide partners with a common strategy, tools and guidelines that facilitate their participation and the optimal implementation of the plan;
3. Identify key messages that resonate to different target audiences;
4. Establish meaningful evaluation criteria for monitoring the effectiveness of the plan;
5. Describe ways of collaborating with other related EU-projects.

The impact and reach of the actions described here will be scaffolded by D6.4, FEDORA Official Video (M12), D6.5 FEDORA Podcast (M24) and D6.6 Policy brief (M24).

5. DEVELOPING FEDORA'S VISUAL IDENTITY

Visual identity refers to a cohesive and robust frame built around visual communication to deliver contents to specific target audiences. It comprises diverse elements of visual communication: logo, fonts, colour palette, images and icons, that come together under one united aesthetic.

FEDORA'S visual identity will be utilized along the project's lifetime. The details of the use and applications of its logo and all its possibilities are collated in the document called "FEDORA branding guidelines". This document will be shared with all partners at the same time of the submission of this deliverable.

These branding guidelines were developed by the graphic designer Valentina Marcon, team member of formicablu. A complete version is downloadable here: [Branding Guidelines](#)

5.1 LOGO

The process

A gallery of different proposals of logos and visual mockups was presented to the consortium during the KOM, in October 2020.

FEDORA

After a lively discussion, modifications of the two most appreciated ideas were developed and further circulated among the consortium.

Few rounds later of further refinements, the final logo represented in Fig. 2 was selected as the best one to characterise FEDORA identity.

Rationale of the selected logo

FEDORA's logo represents the movement of creative minds, the flow of ideas that transit different pathways that are part of a body of knowledge. It is inspired by the Italian artist Fausto Melotti.

5. 1 APPLICATIONS

In the folder Templates, partners will access the set of templates where the branding guidelines are applied and ready to be used for different purposes. There are Agenda, Deliverables and Presentation templates to be used with MS Word software. They are downloadable and easy to adapt to the needed contexts.

 1_BRAND IDENTITY MANUAL

 2_LOGO

 3_LETTERHEAD

 4_AGENDA TEMPLATE

 5_DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

 6_PRESENTATION TEMPLATE

6. FEDORA WEBSITE, WWW.FEDORA-PROJECT.EU

The project's website is an important window to the world and the place where project partners and the different actors involved throughout the project will be able to access FEDORA's materials, news and learn about its development and phases.

The website represents the project's spirit, enhancing its future-oriented ethos. It is the gateway to learn about its structure, participants, activities and public deliverables.

The website displays all the pages required by EU H2020 projects describing the project mission, goals, WPs, partners, deliverables and results.

It will display a Journaling section, where the project will be regularly journaled by formicablu communication team with all partners' active contribution and occasionally selected relevant external contributors. Contributions will be in the shape of texts, images, audio stories, video stories, comments, curation posts. The objective is to collate and make available all the relevant literature and examples behind FEDORA research and actions. Its post-project online availability will be guaranteed for at least two years.

It also showcases inspiring stories, and news that inform about the project's main achievements, fostering collaborations and interactions with organisations and individuals with interest in science education and its branches.

7. FEDORA BRAND BOOK

The Brand book is provided to all partners, with all indications for the visual execution of the logo and the project's visual identity.

FEDORA

Brand manual

This book provides a set of guidelines for visual execution under the FEDORA brand.

This is a living document that outlines recommendations for **logo** usage, color and typography.

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4	Logo overview
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Logo overview

FEDORA

FE DO RA

FEDORA

F E D O R A

Logo overview

DOR

In all formats, the logo should be surrounded by white space equivalent to one of the logo's "F's," as demonstrated here. Always use the provided logo lockups, which were optimized to highlight the brand identity.

EDORA

Logo mark

The FEDORA logo mark can occasionally be used on its own in certain busy applications.

It can also be used as a design element. Regardless of application, the logo mark should always have ample space around it and should always be in palette originals colors.

F

F

F

Colors

Primary palette

RA

FEDOR
A

FEDO

C 72
M 0
Y 68
K 0

R 53
G 179
B 116

#35b374

C 0
M 0
Y 0
K 100

R 0
G 0
B 0

#000000

C 8 8
M 34
Y 88
K 27

R 19
G 101
B 58

#13653a

C 0
M 0
Y 0
K 0

R 255
G 255
B 255

#ffffff

YES

YES

YES

FEDORA

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FEDORA

YES

YES

NO

NO

A
a

Secondary palette

RA

FEDOR
A

FEDO

C 9
M 96
Y 41
K 1

R 214
G 33
B 92

#d6215c

C 0
M 38
Y 76
K 0

R 250
G 175
B 75

#faaf4b

C 75
M 8
Y 44
K 0

R 34
G 167
B 156

#22a79e

Please don't apply this palette
to the logo, but only for
backgrounds and for
secondary elements on
website and
publications (see examples below)

NO

F

NO

F

NO

F

YES

FEDORA

YES

YES

FEDORA

NO

FEDORA

NO

NO

FEDORA

Typography

**Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg
Hh Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo
Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv
Ww Xx Yy Zz
1234567890
|!"£\$%&/()=?***

Bold

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg Hh Jj Kk Ll
Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu Vv
Ww Xx Yy Zz 1234567890
|!"£\$%&/()=?*

Regular

Aa Bb Cc Dd Ee Ff Gg
Hh Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn
Oo Pp Qq Rr Ss Tt Uu
Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz
1234567890
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Light

manual

Application

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F RA

FE

Minimum recommended size
12 mm x 16,1mm

Documents

margin: 2 cm

DDORA

Deliverabl e 1.0

FEDORA

Dissemination plan

Lato Bold 33 pt Lato Bold 16 pt

Version 1.0

Lato Bold 12 pt Lato Light 12pt

Due date: Insert text here

Actual submission date: Insert text here

Project start date: Insert text here - Duration: Insert text here

Workpackage

concerned: Insert text here **Concerned**

Re-entry 1,27cm

workpackage leader:

Insert text here **Task**

leader: Insert text here

Dissemination level:

- PU: Insert text here
- X CO: Insert text here
- CI: Insert text here

FEDOR
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Cover page elements

PAGE
PAGE
26

1. Introduction

Scientific and technological development has been driving fast societal changes and the educational systems are struggling to keep up the pace of such transformations. As a result, youth do not find in education the resources needed to construct empowering visions of their future and develop competences to navigate a complex, fragile and fast-changing society. Effective science education for future generations is urgently needed. The EU-funded FEDORA project aims to develop a future-oriented model enabling formal and informal science education to offer young people

Lato Bold 12 pt

foresight, imaginative and action competences. Specifically, the project will enable research in science education to develop methodologies that target the main factors of present misalignment between educational systems and society. Recommendations for anticipatory policies will then be formulated for the creation of new, visionary attitudes on open schooling and institutional transformations.

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1,25

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Page elements

PAGE
PAGE
26

Table 1 - Communication and Impact Working Group (CI-WG)

Role	Role	Role	Name	Surname
Coordinator	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text
Member	Insert text	Insert text	Marcassa	Insert text
Member	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text
Member	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text
Member	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text
Member	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text
Member	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text
Member	UT Insert text	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text
Alternate member	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text	Insert text
Group of Mentors, according to the role specified in the project (see above)				

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Table example

PAGE
PAGE
26

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Website

Resources

2 cm

A4 page

2 cm

Books

News

Events

Resources

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Every resource has a color

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DORA

thank you!